

The Global Terrorism Threats to the State Security

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Abstract:

This research paper is an attempt to investigate the phenomenon of global terrorism and its threats to the states security. The study clarifies the concept of terrorism and its definition, then the categories of terrorism. Next, it shows how terrorism became a global phenomenon through the historical overview of international terrorism and the theories explaining it and its current situation. The causes of international terrorism are the economic cause, social cause, religions cause, political cause and other causes. The study investigated the effects of international terrorism and its implications on international peace, states security and what had been done yet internationally in fighting terrorism. The study analyses the causes and the theoretical frameworks that stand behind the phenomenon. The study recommended to face the international terrorism through developing national strategies and strengthening international, regional and bilateral cooperation and coordination with the international counter-terrorism system in the context of the resolutions of the UN and building national intellectual system to confront terrorism and solving the major political conflicts which have direct impact on the terrorism.

Keywords

Global terrorism, Threats, State Security, Causes.

Introduction

In the year 2016, there were 1,441 terrorist attacks which caused 14,356 fatalities with a bigger number of injuries. Terrorism is one of the most dangerous phenomena that facing the international society. The current situation that the world lives in, especially after the end of the Cold War, put terrorism combating on the top priorities of all countries. The International Community realized the merging danger and created special military and experts teams and high budgets to fight it.

The observed phenomenon shows that we are living in an age of global terrorism facing increasing actions and brutality that kills more and more innocent people with no mercy like in the past. The nature and type of terrorism had become more daring, varied and complex. The terrorist organizations and groups became very elusive and easy to be found in anywhere on the surface of the planet. There is a real need for strong combat with any means. But before combating, studies must be conducted fully to

understand the causes of terrorism. The fundamental causes can be prevented if there is true will to do so. Social justice, religion moderation, political and economic reforms and equality and other procedures are the demands of nations. Other causes of terrorism are found like ethnic and race discrimination as we will see inside. But, the one goal these organizations are demanding is in political field, nothing else. All possible types of violence are used to draw attention and force governments to accept them and meet their needs. The significance of the problem is that is a worldwide. The changing happened in the world make via the spread of communication technologies and people movement helped a lot in this aspect.

This paper is an attempt to investigate the phenomenon of global terrorism and its threats to the states security. First we will clarify the concept of terrorism and its definition, then the categories of terrorism. The next step is to show how terrorism became a global phenomenon through the historical overview of international terrorism and the theories explaining it and its current situation. The causes of international terrorism will be shown which they are the economic cause, social cause, religions cause, political cause and other causes. The fourth step is to get into the core of this paper is to investigate the effects of international terrorism and its implications on international peace, states security and what had been done yet internationally in fighting terrorism. The study analyses the causes and the theoretical frameworks that stand behind the phenomenon. The study attempts to know the terrorism reflections on the world peace and state security. Finally, the study arrives at some recommendations to face the international terrorism.

The Clarification of Terrorism

Violence usage accompanied human being has been used since the early times of recorded history and its roots in the deep history of humans. We practiced all types of violence starting with threatening, using sticks and stones and ending with nuclear weapons in comprehensive wars. All these different sorts of violence caused pain which terrifies people to be exposed to it. It is a terrifying experiment to be unsecure in life of unseen danger

hanging somewhere around and may cause death or any other pain in any time, without alarm. The victims have no any sin for what they had exposed to. Terrorism stands in this corner against societies and governments using unlawful violence to accomplish political goals in its own agendas.

Terrorism is totally different from regular crime because of its strong political prosperities. The definition of terrorism can vary from people to people due to the differences in standpoints. One person's terrorist can be another freedom fighter (Ganor, 2002). So that, the various interests of countries give various understandings of terrorism. There is no consensus on defining terrorism among countries.

The terrorism definition depends mainly on three components. Simply and without any complexity, terrorism is using types of violence by a group of people against others to achieve political goals. But, this is not enough and not convenient because it is mixed with freedom struggle which is the fight of one nation against another occupying nation to gain liberty and self-determine. Self-determine is a basic right which had been put in the international signed conventions especially the United Nations conventions of Human Rights (Payne, 2007). In opposite of terrorism, self-determine principle in protected by the international laws and it is a core element of nationalism and decolonization's movements.

In 2004, a High-Level Panel on Threats, Challenges and Change composed of independent experts and convened by the Secretary-General of the United Nations called states to set aside their differences and to adopt, in the text of a proposed Comprehensive Convention on International Terrorism, the following political "description of terrorism":

"any action, in addition to actions already specified by the existing conventions on aspects of terrorism, the Geneva Conventions and Security Council resolution 1566 (2004), that is intended to cause death or serious bodily harm to civilians or non-combatants, when the

purpose of such an act, by its nature or context, is to intimidate a population, or to compel a Government or an international organization to do or to abstain from doing any act." (U.N. 2004).

Walter Laqueur defines it as: **"Terrorism constitutes the illegitimate use of force to achieve a political objective when innocent people are targeted"**. (Coady, et al, 2002).

The Characteristics of International Terrorism:

The elements of all terrorisms' actions are the same, in general. But, there are changes happened that made the terrorism spreads worldwide intensively. The terrorist organizations manage to adapt and adjust to the new world's changes. They core of terrorism did not changed. It still depends on propaganda, political group gain and violence against innocent people. Terrorist took the best advantage of revolution in the information technology in mass and social media, communications, travelling and monitory system. Belief in the terrorist groups is a very strong component (Conte, 2010). The more hardliners there are the more loyalty found no matter it is a religious or ethnic groups they are. The majority of these organizations' members had been raised on the fundamental ideas, thoughts and principles. Brutality is found in the attacks of such organizations like Al-Qaida, ISIS and Lord's Résistance Army in Africa. Some of the organizations are about to be terrorist because they are at the edge of violence.

The new characteristics of International terrorism can be summarized in:

1. Globalization: in the last 15 years, groups of terrorist spread in South Asia, Middle East, Africa, Europe, United States and other places around the world. The level of terrorism moved to regional and global levels. It is not restricted in one region. The movement of refugees planted these groups everywhere. Originally they reach new shelters with their own thoughts

(Ganor, 2002). They had been forced to move not only because of wars and conflicts, but also pushed by other factors like poverty, social justice and legal and illegal immigration.

2. Individualism: a recent phenomenon who do solo attack without any clear connections to the terrorist groups. They had been called the Lone-wolves who prepares and commits violent acts alone, outside of any command structure and without material assistance from any group. However, he or she may be influenced or motivated by the ideology and beliefs of an external group, and may act in support of such a group (Fenstermacher, et, 2010).
3. Internet: The terrorist organizations depend on media in spreading their thoughts. New developed communication technologies provide easy way to reach easy target of audience. They had highly skilled and professional cadres who can produce the best suitable materials. Website, social media accounts TV channels and radios are found on internet. Some of them had hackers to sneak into their enemies websites. Terrorists can communicate easily via free technology (Kydd, et, 2006).

Terrorism as an International Phenomenon:

Historical overview of international Terrorism:

The issue of terrorism started to rise up in the first half of the 20th century where two major events influenced the nature of conflict to the present day, but not in the international level. The two World Wars affected inspired and inflamed passions and hopes of nationalists throughout the world. Nationalism played the major role in the rise intensively during the early and middle of the 20th century throughout the world. It became an especially powerful force in the subject peoples of various colonial empires (Jenkins, (2006). Although opposition and resistance were common in many colonial territories, and sometimes resulted in open warfare, nationalist identities became a focal point for these actions. The colonial power

executed those who chose terror helplessly (Bergesen and Lizardo, 2004).

During the Cold War the major powers' support of partisan and resistance organizations using terrorist tactics was viewed as an acceptance of their legitimacy. It seemed that civilians had become legitimate targets, despite any rules forbidding it. The bi-polar world of the Cold War changed perception of conflicts the world over. Relatively minor confrontations took on significance as arenas where the superpowers could compete without risking escalation to full nuclear war. The rebels (Terrorists) fought instead of the East and the West in many parts of the world. Terrorism was more of a tactical choice by leaders of nationalist insurgencies and revolutions (Cole, (2003).

The age of modern terrorism (Internalization of Terror) had begun in 1968 when the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine (PFLP) hijacked an El Al airlines flying from Tel Aviv to Rome. The founder of PFLP, Dr. George Habash observed that the level of coverage was tremendously greater than battles with Israeli soldiers in their previous area of operations. **"At least the world is talking about us now"** (www.terrorism-research.com). Then cooperation began to show up between the rebellious groups in planning, training, bombing and attacking.

As many scholars agreed on, the largest act of international terrorism occurred on 9/11 in a set of co-ordinate attacks on the United States of America, where Islamic terrorists hijacked civilian airplanes and used them to attack the World Trade Centre (WTC) towers in New York City and the Pentagon in Washington, DC. The effects of 9/11 had a significant impact on the American psyche and led to global reverberations (Rostow, 2001). Many other major terrorist attacks have also occurred in New Delhi, Bali, London subway bombings, Spain, attacks in Mumbai, Nigeria, Pakistan, France, Turkey, Germany and other places all over the world where now about than 168 terrorist organizations are enlisted (wikipedia.org).

Theories of Terrorism

Terrorism is a political violence for a group of people who see that these terroristic actions are for their benefits. Scholars initiated several theories in attempt to explain the terrorism phenomenon.

1. Marxist theory says that the class struggle occurs at a certain stage of the development of societies. The contradictions between social forces based on the ownership of means of production. This class contradiction ultimately leads to political violence represented by the revolution of the proletariat over the bourgeois class that owns the means of production (Robison, et al, 2006).

2. Functional theory: it sees that the revolutionary situation comes when the political system as a whole is inconsistent with society. This occurs when society suffers from multiple functional deficits and thus cannot perform its functions resulting in multiple pressures for change (Robison, et, 2006).

3. Theory of relative deprivation: The logic of this theory focuses on social pressures or adversity which is resembled in transfer, shift of land ownership, hunger, poverty, frustration and discontent. These pressures are seen as the direct and final instigator of acts of violence against the colonial regime, or the tyrannical authority in the independent state.

4. The J-Curve Theory: The J-Curve theory links political violence to certain variables such as growing expectations, where violence occurs after a long period of economic prosperity, which the expectations of citizens are increased.

5. Theory of rapid economic growth: Based on the assumption of a mutual effect between economic conditions and political stability in the state (Hoffman, et al, 2009).

6. Theory of political armament: This theory believes that politics is a field of competition between different groups which seek to own power then wealth and social status. The outcome of this competition is determined by the balance of resources available to group.

7. Theory of comparative history: It considers that revolutions are not limited the motives of participants, but in structural situations, and the model of relations between the states and between groups within society. The direct cause of the revolutions is an international and local deficit (Brynjar and Skjølberg, 2000).

The above theories are explaining the terrorism depending on each understanding of reasons and motivations of rejecting the societies. The most convincing theories are the functional and relative deprivation theories. Both of them are focusing on the elements of political, economic and societal factors which motivate the groups to take actions against their targets to achieve special political goals.

The Causes of the international Terrorism:

Through investigating the causes behind the terrorism's spread in the globe, three main reasons are found, politics, economics and fundamentalism rise causes. Of course, the spread of terrorism is affected directly with the globalization process which took place at the end of the 20th century.

Political Causes:

Political goals form the core of terrorists groups' motivations. The belief in political rights to be practiced whether with the share of others or independently during and after the era of decolonization triggered the spark of international terrorism.

On July 22, 1946, the rebellious right-wing Zionist group, Irgun, carried out an offensive against the British by bombing the British Administrative Headquarters for Palestine, which was housed at the King David Hotel. This terrorist campaign concluded with the death of 91 people from various nationalities and injured 46 others. This is considered the deadliest terrorist attack to occur during the British Mandate era from 1920 to 1948 (Charters, 2007).

The Palestinian- Israeli conflict resembled the beginning of shifting the conflict from locally to internationally. The Palestinian political parties went through several attacks against Israeli targets in Europe by

hijacking planes in 1968 and taking hostages in Munich-Germany in 1973 during the Olympic Games (Jenkins, 1985). The attacker wanted to draw the attention of the world to their own demands.

Also known as the ‘Lockerbie Bombing,’ on December 21, 1988 in a Pan Am flight from London Heathrow Airport. The Boeing 747 exploded killing all 243 passengers aboard as well as its 16 crewmembers before it crashed in Lockerbie, Scotland killing 11 more on the ground. Investigation resulted in the arrest of 2 Libyan nationals who were handed over by the Gaddafi. Libya paid compensation to the victims’ families, though maintaining that he did not personally order the attack which resulted in more conspiracy theories (Plachta, 2001).

The series of terroristic attack continued till the present time with a larger number of terrorist groups and organizations. The actions foreign policy of state also evoked the appetite of terrorist organizations for more attacks such as Russian-Chechnya and USA in Somalia, Iraq and Afghanistan. The media played a very excellent role in letting the world to know about these groups and their demands. Still, the world has 186 enlisted terrorist organizations with various back grounds. Now days, twenty organization were removed from the list of terrorism due to various reasons which the leaving armed struggle behind and other political reasons the main cause such as PLO, Communist Party of the Philippines and African National Congress (wikipedia.org).

Economical Causes:

The continued existence of an unjust international economic order helped in creation a state of constant anger and hostility among the various peoples of the world. Foreign exploitation of national natural resources which produced by the dependence policies put more burdens on nationals to act against that. As a result, poverty, hunger, misery, disappointment or frustration came out with anger followed by resistance to stop the deterioration of the national economies. The dominance of the major powers

over the world economy pushed by hard competition make it easy to find a reason for holding attacks against others. An example for that the attacks on petrol and gas pipe lines in Nigeria 2005 (Onuoha, 2008).). Another example is the piracy actions by Somalia terrorist groups on oil tankers in the Gulf of Aden which stated in 2018 (Marchione and Johnson, 2013).

The Rise of Fundamentalism:

The rise of fundamentalism is a major reason in the spread of international terrorism. These movements rejected the modern secular societies which separate religion and politics. Whatever the politicians or the pundits claim, people all over the world are demonstrating that they want to see religion reflected more prominently in public life. As part of their campaign, fundamentalists tend to withdraw from mainstream society to create enclaves of pure faith.

The world witnessed the rise of religious fundamentalism through the terroristic actions done by the religions' followers whether it is Islam, Judaism, Christianity, Hinduism or Buddhism. Suicide bombing and genocide massacre are done by name of religion. The fundamentalist groups share the same categories; faith and salvation (Rogers, et, 2007).

Religious terrorism which is executed by those whose inspirations and aims have a overwhelming religious impact is established in the confusion of theological epithets, or it could be the consequence of outrageous types of delusion that may change reality, and subsequently subject an individual or a group of people to mutilated forms of religious certainties and episodes like ‘just war theory’, liberation theology, Inquisitions and the Crusades. Religious terrorism consists of acts that terrify; the definition of which is provided by the witnesses the ones terrified and not by the party committing the act; joined by a religious motivation, justification, organization, or world view (Odhiambo, 2014).

The big facilitator that shifted the terrorism to the international level is the scientific advancement of

information technologies. It is a double edge weapon. It can be used for fighting terrorism. In the same time, it can be used as a mean of spreading ideas and thoughts and connection means through countless free and easy communication applications.

The Terrorism Threats to State Security:

The Terrorism Threats to National Security:

The international terrorism is one of the most dangerous and horrible crimes that have spread in our modern world. It has become universal in its characteristic. Peoples of the world suffer from the sequences in varying degrees and different forms. In the current globalized era, it has gained a new dimension in terms of its breadth and influence.

Terrorism is a means of achieving often political objectives by terror. Therefore, Terrorism is a flagrant violation of human rights, international law and legal norms on the one hand, and customary and religious norms on the other hand. It is leading to horror, fear and panic among the general public or a group of particular people. This poses a threat to international peace and sates security and societies and exposes the internal and international stability and friendly relations between nations. Today, terrorism has become a weapon used by some countries as an alternative to conventional wars in its struggle and its pursuit of its strategic interests and objectives, regardless of the legitimacy of the means leading to it and sometimes resorting to direct and indirect terrorist acts to achieve its objectives (Mohammad, 2011).

International terrorism appears to be a fundamental indicator of the violation and taking off many of the original human rights guaranteed by religions, conventions and charters through international human rights law, in particular the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, as well as the Covenants on Civil and Political Rights (Mohammad, 2011).

The best example for terrorism is what is happening in Syria. The civilians are easy targets for all kinds of attacks

and weapons. Fear and panic are everywhere. The stare of Syria became a unsafe country. The destruction occurs various forms may result in the destruction of homes and burning property and the causing of material losses. Iraq is another good example for the insecure state. The Iraqi government is unable to secure its citizens, borders and economy. Syria, Iraq, Libya and Yemen seem to be the terror mania land. Refugees fled away to the neighboring countries. Some of them hold the seeds of terrorism with them.

Terrorism has both direct and indirect effects on security of state's economy. It is noted that as government spends much on the security in the country, businesses have become vulnerable to terrorist targets, with important implications for the operations and performance of multinational firms. For example for that terrorism incidents affected the economy and business in Nigeria. Terror incidents also occur in Nigeria just like other countries globally leading to significant socio-economic consequences. The terror actions and violence form unsecure environment for economic investment in any country (Najaf and Najaf 2016).

The Terrorism Threats to International Security:

As a result of the spread of terrorism in most the world's countries, the international peace became threatened directly. Fighting terrorism jumped on the top of priority list of countries. The United Nations panel on Threats, challenges and Change has said that there are six types of threat where terrorism is one of them. Lead by the UN and the super powers and their allies are determining to terminate terrorism. The world's reaction to terrorism after the September, 11th 2001 attacks by Al-Qaida divided the countries into two parts (4). The Security Council Resolution 1368 reiterates the right of self-defense by a state specifically against "terrorist attacks" (para. 3). The Council clearly identifies "international terrorism as a threat to international peace and security" against which "individual or collective self-defense may be exercised (Franck, 2001).

The world's countries continued the diplomatic campaigns to provide more cooperation in fighting terrorism. The governments are very convinced that they are in targets lists of attacks of terrorist organizations and groups. Wars had been done even before 2001 New York attack in Somalia Panama then Afghanistan, Iraq, Libya, Yemen, Syria and lately, the Turkey coup 2016 whom had been accused with terrorism.

As a part of terrorism many countries made changes in their local laws. Their parliaments ratified it easily. More responsibilities and power to take actions are given to government because terrorism is very scary especially when it happens close to homes and not in some faraway place and more security is demanded. Spying, collecting and storing personal information of citizens that might lead to possible terrorists or plans. Fighting terrorism is affecting everyone regardless whoever he is. The collation to combat terrorism made compulsory cooperation and response from major Information Technologies companies to give their coding secrets to the authorities. Not only this, but also very advanced programs had been produced to register any click or voice call (Perl, 2016).

The mission to face the global terrorism is too hard due to the three different dimensions. The first is worldwide public support. The second is global reach. The third and much more important is the global political aspirations of certain terrorist groups (ONAY & KYRIAKIDIS, 2008).

The United Nations established a working group under the name of the United Nations Counter-Terrorism Implementation Task Force (CTITF) by the Secretary-General in 2005 to ensure overall coordination and coherence in the counter-terrorism efforts of the United Nations system (United Nations. CTITF, 2009).

Conclusion:

Terrorism is the consequence of political, economic and fundamental causes. It flourished by the help of information technology revolution. The terrorist organizations use the world's map during discussions and

planning. Current trends and patterns of touristic attacks started well before 9/11 a long time ago.

There are two real and serious threats from terrorists to any country's security. The first is from terrorist acts themselves, which could cause mass casualties, severe economic loss, and social dislocation local society. The second is from the possibility of inappropriate or disproportionate responses to the terrorist threat that can do more damage to the fabric of society than terrorists would be likely to do. So that. Terrorism forms big threats to the state security in two levels, nationally and internationally. As for the national level, the terrorism actions lead to insecure societies. People first demand is security in homes, work, transportations, food and all other aspects of daily live. The existence of terrorists among people produces horror between civilians. The security of state's economy is highly affected by unsafe environment for investments.

Recommendations:

1. Developing national strategies of each country to combat terrorism based on the defense and intelligence, undermine the terrorists' thoughts, drying up the sources and the capabilities of law enforcement.
2. Strengthening international, regional and bilateral cooperation and coordination with the international counter-terrorism system in the context of the resolutions of the UN General Assembly and the UN Security Council to confront the threatens to international and regional peace and internal stability of countries. Countries should seek to establish legal frameworks that allow flexible exchange of practical information between competent authorities at the local, regional and international levels especially money laundering and combating the financing of terrorism.
3. Building national intellectual system to confront terrorism, such as the fundamentalism thoughts and detection of the danger of thought. Focusing on

awareness among people of the culture of tolerance and respect for others within the plans and programs appropriate and national strategy to combat terrorism to be in line with plans in other areas to counter terrorism.

4. Solving the major political conflicts which have direct impact on the terrorism thoughts such as the Palestinian – Israeli conflict on the bases of just and equality due the international legitimacy.

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